

1 **STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION OF**
2 **Ni/ALUMINA REFORMING CATALYSTS**
3 **ACTIVATED AT HIGH TEMPERATURES**

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21 **ABSTRACT**

22 This paper is devoted to the characterisation of Ni/alumina reforming catalysts. A
23 special attention was paid to the control of the catalytic properties by the synthesis route
24 of bulk and supported catalysts. In this sense it was shown that the massive formation of
25 NiAl_2O_4 phase, associated with low $\text{NiO}/\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4$ molar ratios on the catalyst surface,
26 due to a calcination step at high temperatures was notably beneficial for obtaining
27 highly dispersed nickel catalysts (with a Ni crystallite size of 6 nm) after severe
28 reduction at 850 °C. This activation procedure did not affect both textural and acidic
29 properties to a large extent. Thus, among the investigated nickel catalysts the
30 70% $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ sample exhibited the best performance in the steam reforming of
31 methane.

32

33 Keywords: nickel aluminate, alumina supported nickel catalyst, characterisation,
34 methane steam reforming

35 1. INTRODUCTION

36 Conventional catalysts for methane reforming reactions generally contain noble metals
37 (Rh, Ru, Pd, Pt) supported on oxides [1-3]. As viable alternatives Ni/alumina catalysts
38 have attracted much attention in the last years because of their lower cost [4-6]. These
39 typically exhibit a good activity but they are very sensitive to the alteration of the
40 metal/support interactions during reaction. Thus, research has been focused on the
41 preparation of active and stable (with a reduced sintering and coking) catalysts by
42 varying the synthesis routes to achieve high nickel dispersion and/or to favour specific
43 nickel coordinations [7-9]. In addition, many works have been dedicated to examine the
44 influence of the nickel particle size on the catalytic activity [10-12]. In this sense, Zhai
45 et al. indicated that small particles in strong interaction with supports lead to good
46 dispersion, thereby having a slight tendency to sintering and coking [11].

47 On the other hand, much attention has been also given to analysing the active phases
48 laying on the Ni/alumina surface [8,13,14]. It is known that at high temperatures
49 (≥ 700 °C), nickel is incorporated into the structure of alumina to form a NiAl_2O_4 - Al_2O_3
50 solid solution together with NiO. The catalytic behaviour of these Ni/alumina systems is
51 not yet well understood because of the complex interactions between nickel and the
52 alumina support when the catalyst is working [7]. For example, despite the fact that
53 reduced nickel aluminate is remarkably active in reforming reactions, it may be re-
54 oxidised during the reactions with a source of oxygen leading to inactive NiAl_2O_4 [14].
55 These redox processes provoke notable superficial changes and are generally
56 accompanied by a decay of the catalytic activity.

57 According to many authors, the creation of a nickel aluminate layer between the nickel
58 particles and the alumina support may suppress the sintering of the nickel particles.
59 Hence, Bolt et al. studied the role of a NiAl_2O_4 intermediate layer in the sintering

60 behaviour of Ni/Al₂O₃ and explained the least sintering of Ni/NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples
61 by the deposition of Ni particles on top of NiAl₂O₄ islands [15], whereas a continuous
62 interfacial layer of NiAl₂O₄ did not inhibit sintering. In their study of the
63 17.9 wt.%Ni/NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃/alloy catalyst for steam reforming of methane, Zhou et al.
64 obtained an excellent activity [14]. They found that the activity was favoured by the
65 presence of the interfacial NiAl₂O₄ layer by interrupting the formation of Ni-spinel and
66 keeping the size of Ni particles. Lif et al. showed that the formation of nickel aluminate
67 by sequential impregnation, with high temperature calcination in between, of the nickel
68 precursors gave a more stable catalyst compared to simple impregnated 10Ni/alumina
69 used as reference sample [16]. Salhi et al. prepared several mixed oxides close to
70 NiAl₂O₄ with different amounts of NiO excess. They reported that the high activity
71 obtained with NiAl₂O₄ in steam reforming of methane was essentially attributed to the
72 high dispersion of nickel on the spinel [17].

73 In our previous study, devoted to examine the catalytic behaviour of the bulk nickel
74 aluminate in the partial oxidation of methane, it was found that the nickel aluminate
75 phase promoted an efficient reduction of the Ni²⁺ species leading to a notable oxidative
76 conversion of methane and a marked stability during extended time on stream [18]. It
77 was then concluded that the spinel appeared to be as a basis for tuning the properties of
78 the active phases and owing to its low surface area, its dispersion on an appropriate
79 oxide carrier may thus be considered as an interesting alternative instead of the bulk
80 form.

81 The present study is an extension of this recent work mentioned above. It is focused on
82 the characterisation of NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalysts activated at high temperatures. Special
83 attention is paid to the determination of interactions of nickel species using BET
84 measurements, X-ray diffraction, diffuse reflectance spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron

85 spectroscopy, temperature programmed reduction with hydrogen and transmission
86 electron microscopy. In addition, the acid properties of the catalysts are examined by
87 temperature programmed desorption of ammonia. This NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ system prepared
88 by the co-impregnation method, calcined at 850 °C to obtain a mixture of NiO+NiAl₂O₄
89 phases and then reduced at 850 °C, to our knowledge, has not been yet investigated in
90 methane reforming reactions. The correlation between the catalytic activity in these
91 reactions and the characterisation results will be presented in the next part of this paper.
92 Even so, some preliminary results on the performance of investigated catalysts in the
93 steam reforming of methane are given.

94

95 **2. EXPERIMENTAL**

96 *2.1. Catalysts preparation*

97 NiAl₂O₄ loaded alumina samples were prepared by the wet co-impregnation method
98 using solutions (50 cm³) containing a mixture of Ni(CH₃-COO)₂·4H₂O (1.8 g – 5.3 g,
99 Aldrich) and Al(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (5.3 g – 15.9 g, Fluka) to obtain 15 wt.% and 70 wt.% of
100 stoichiometric NiAl₂O₄ supported on alumina (5 g of γ-Al₂O₃, SA 6173, Saint-Gobain,
101 133 m² g⁻¹, 0.3-0.5 mm). The samples were labelled 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and
102 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and the corresponding nickel loadings were 5 and 24 wt.%Ni,
103 respectively. The catalyst denoted as 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ was prepared by three successive
104 impregnations (5 g of γ-Al₂O₃) with an ethanolic solution (50 cm³) of nickel acetate
105 (2.1 g) containing approximately 9 wt.% of nickel. The excess of ethanol was
106 evaporated off to dryness in a rotary evaporator at 50 °C. The catalyst was calcined at
107 850 °C after each impregnation.

108 Bulk nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄-D; the letter D was used in order to distinguish the
109 catalyst from the NiAl₂O₄ crystalline phase) was synthesised according to the following

110 method. Two aqueous solutions (50 cm^3) containing $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (7 g) and
111 $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (21.2 g) were separately prepared. Then they were mixed (leading to a
112 mixture with the desired 1:2 Ni/Al molar ratio), and evaporated on a hot plate ($150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).
113 NiO was prepared by simple calcination in air of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 g). All the
114 samples were dried at $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ overnight and then calcined at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in static air for 4 h
115 at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Pellets of bulk NiO and $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$ samples were
116 prepared by a process of compressing the powders into flakes in a hydraulic press
117 (Specac), crushing and sieving (0.3-0.5 mm).

118

119 2.2. Characterisation techniques

120 Wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF) analysis was carried out with
121 AXIOS PANalytical spectrometer equipped with a Rh tube. Prior to analysis the
122 samples were prepared by the fusion method using a Spectromelt A12 flux supplied by
123 Merck.

124 Textural properties were evaluated from the nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms,
125 determined at $-196 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a Micromeritics TRISTAR II 3020 apparatus. The specific
126 areas of the samples were determined in line with the standard BET procedure, using
127 nitrogen adsorption taken in the relative equilibrium pressure interval of 0.03-0.3. Mean
128 pore size was calculated using the BJH method. The samples were previously degassed
129 overnight under nitrogen flow.

130 The morphologies of the reduced samples were observed using a JEOL JSM-7000F
131 scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with a Schottky field emission gun
132 (FEG). Secondary electron images were taken at 20 kV and a current intensity of
133 $1.1 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ } \text{\AA}$ was employed using a working distance of 10 mm. To provide electrical

134 conductivity the samples were coated with a coal graphite layer (10 nm) by evaporation
135 using Quorum Q150T Sputter Coater.

136 X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were conducted on a X'PERT-MPD X-ray
137 diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The X-ray tube was
138 operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The samples were scanned between 10° (2θ) and 70° -
139 80° (2θ), and the X-ray diffraction line positions were determined with a step size of
140 0.01° (2θ) and a counting time of 2.5 s per step. Phase identification was conducted by
141 comparison with JCPDS (Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards) database
142 cards. The oxidation states and the coordination of Ni species were evaluated by diffuse
143 reflectance UV-vis spectroscopy (UV-vis-DRS) with a UV-vis-NIR Cary 5000
144 apparatus coupled to Diffuse Reflectance Internal 2500 within a range of 350-2500 nm.

145 The acid properties of the catalysts in terms of total acidity and acid strength
146 distribution were evaluated by temperature-programmed desorption of NH_3 (NH_3 -TPD)
147 at 100°C and subsequent desorption with increasing temperature. These experiments
148 were carried out with a Setaram Setsys Evolution thermobalance under atmospheric
149 pressure coupled to a Pfeiffer Prisma mass spectrometer (TGA-MS). Prior to adsorption
150 experiments, the samples (60 mg) were first pre-treated in a helium stream at 850°C
151 ($10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) and then cooled to 100°C ($40^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$). Later, the NH_3 adsorption step
152 was performed by admitting a flow of $10\%\text{NH}_3/\text{He}$ at 100°C up to saturation.
153 Subsequently, the samples were exposed to a flow of helium ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) for 90 min
154 at 100°C to remove reversibly and physically bound ammonia from the surface. Finally,
155 desorption was carried out from 100 to 850°C at heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in a He
156 stream ($50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$). This temperature was maintained for 1 h until the adsorbate was
157 completely desorbed. The reduced samples, before NH_3 adsorption, were reduced at
158 850°C ($10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) during 2 h in a $5\%\text{H}_2/\text{Ar}$ flow.

159 Redox behaviour was examined by temperature-programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR), and
160 the experiments were conducted on a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument.
161 Firstly, all the samples (30 mg) were pre-treated in an oxygen stream (5% O_2/He) at
162 550 °C for 1 h and then cooled to room temperature. The reducing gas used in all
163 experiments was 5% H_2/Ar , with a flow rate of $50 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The temperature range
164 explored was from room temperature to 950 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} . This
165 temperature was maintained for 1 h. The water produced by reduction was trapped in a
166 cold trap, and the consumption of H_2 was quantitatively measured by time integration of
167 the TPR profiles.

168 Calcined nickel samples were additionally characterised by X-ray photoelectron
169 spectroscopy (XPS). XPS measurements were performed with a Phoibos 150 1D-DLD
170 analysis system from Specs, with monochromatic Al $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation (1486.6 eV). The
171 conductivity of the samples was enhanced by the use of an electron flood gun. The
172 samples were not sputter-cleaned before measurement. The hemispheric photoelectron
173 analyser worked with a pass energy of 40 eV for survey scan and 20 eV for detail scan.
174 In order to compare all spectra recorded, the C 1s core level attributed to adventitious
175 carbon present in the samples was used as a reference, whose binding energy was fixed
176 at 284.6 eV. Peaks areas of Ni^{2+} including satellites were fitted with a non-linear least
177 squares fitting program using a properly weighted sum of Lorentzian and Gaussian
178 component curves after background subtraction according to Shirley.

179 High-resolution transmission (HRTEM) and high-angle annular dark-field scanning-
180 transmission (HAADF-STEM) micrographs were obtained using a JEOL-2010F
181 microscope equipped with a field emission gun and operated at an acceleration voltage
182 of 200 kV. The structural resolution of the equipment in the HRTEM mode was
183 0.19 nm at the Scherzer defocus conditions, while the diameter of the probe used in

184 STEM was 0.5 nm at a diffraction camera length of 10 cm. In view of the dependence
185 of the HAADF contrasts on the atomic number of the elements present in the sample,
186 this technique is particularly suitable for investigation into heavy elements, such as
187 nickel, dispersed on light supports. Due to this proportionality, it is possible to
188 unambiguously discriminate between Ni ($Z = 28$) and the cation of the support, Al
189 ($Z = 13$), for accurate determination of the average size distribution of the metal
190 particles. Particle size distribution was obtained from the measurement of at least 450
191 particles, and the average diameter was calculated by $d_M = \sum d_i n_i / \sum n_i$, where n_i is
192 the number of the particles of diameter d_i . Due to the magnetic properties of the
193 samples, the powders were fixed in an Epon resin to prevent the contamination of the
194 electron microscope. The samples were embedded using the routine described by Spurr
195 [19], but without the dehydration step. After fixation, ultrafine (a few ten nm thick)
196 sections were obtained from the polymerised specimens by means of an ultramicrotome.
197 The sections were mounted on copper grids for electron microscopy characterization.

198

199 2.3. *Catalytic activity*

200 Catalytic tests were performed in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor (Microactivity
201 modular laboratory system provided by PID Eng&Tech S.L) operated at atmospheric
202 pressure and fully monitored by computer. The reactor was made of stainless steel with
203 an internal diameter of 9 mm and a height of 305 mm, in which the temperature was
204 controlled with a thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. Typically 0.125 g of catalyst in
205 powdered form (0.3-0.5 mm) was loaded. The catalysts bed was diluted with inert
206 quartz (0.875 g, 1-1.25 mm). A feed gas mixture containing $\text{CH}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{N}_2 = 1/3/6$
207 (mol/mol) was used for which a gas hourly space velocity was maintained at
208 $38400 \text{ ml CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ using Bronkhorst mass flow controllers. Before the reaction, the

209 Ni-based catalysts were *in situ* reduced under 5% H₂/N₂ at 850 °C and noble metal-based
 210 catalysts at 700 °C for 2 h. The catalysts activity, selectivity and stability was recorded
 211 during 12.5 h at varying constant temperature (450 °C/550 °C/650 °C/550 °C/450 °C)
 212 with an accumulated time online of about 63 h. Feed and effluent streams were analysed
 213 online by a MicroGC (Agilent 3000) equipped with a TCD detector. Two columns,
 214 Molecular Sieve 5A and Plot U, were used in a series/bypass arrangement for the
 215 complete separation of H₂, N₂, O₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂. A cold trap at the outlet of the
 216 reactor was used to condense out any water from the product gas stream. On basis of the
 217 molar flow at the inlet and outlet of the reactor, conversion and product yields were
 218 calculated, according to the following equations:

$$219 \quad X (CH_4), \% = \frac{F(CO_{out}) + F(CO_{2,out})}{F(CH_{4,in})} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$220 \quad Y(H_2) = \frac{F(H_{2,out})}{2 \cdot F(CH_{4,in})} \quad (2)$$

$$221 \quad Y(CO) = \frac{F(CO_{out})}{F(CH_{4,in})} \quad (3)$$

$$222 \quad Y(CO_2) = \frac{F(CO_{2,out})}{F(CH_{4,in})} \quad (4)$$

223 The thermodynamic data were calculated via the HSC Chemistry software package by
 224 the GIBBS program using the so-called Gibbs Energy Minimization Method. For these
 225 calculations, only enthalpy, entropy and heat capacity data for all prevailing compounds
 226 were needed. The software calculated the amounts of products at equilibrium under
 227 isothermal and isobaric conditions. The substances to be taken into account in the
 228 calculations, the amount of reactants, the potentially stable phases as well as the
 229 temperature of raw species were specified as input. In addition to solid carbon, the
 230 following substances in the gas phase were considered: CH₄, O₂, N₂, CO, CO₂, H₂ and

231 H₂O. Calculations were performed in the 450-650 °C temperature range at atmospheric
232 pressure. Hence, the GIBBS program found the most stable phase combination and
233 determined the phase composition where the Gibbs energy for the system reached its
234 minimum at constant pressure and temperature.

235

236 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

237 *3.1. Textural properties*

238 The textural properties of the calcined catalysts were examined by nitrogen adsorption-
239 desorption measurements. All the samples exhibited IV-type isotherms, indicating the
240 existence of well-developed mesopores, with significantly reduced hysteresis loops for
241 all the catalysts (Supporting information, Figure S1). The specific surface area, pore
242 volume and average pore size are shown in Table 1. Markedly, the pre-calcination
243 treatment of γ -Al₂O₃ support at 850 °C for 8 h led to a noteworthy decrease in surface
244 area from 212 to 133 m² g⁻¹. Irrespective of the nickel phase (NiO and/or NiAl₂O₄)
245 present on the alumina support, the surface area of the resultant catalysts significantly
246 decreased from 133 to 111 m² g⁻¹ for 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, 91 m² g⁻¹ for 24%Ni/Al₂O₃
247 and 75 m² g⁻¹ for 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ [20]. A simultaneous decrease in pore volume was
248 also found. Interestingly, the bulk NiAl₂O₄-D spinel exhibited a relatively high surface
249 area, close to 60 m² g⁻¹.

250

Table 1

251 Table 1 also includes the specific surface areas of the samples reduced at 850 °C for 2 h.
252 The obtained results showed that, despite the fact that the reduction at 850 °C did not
253 substantially modify the shape of the adsorption isotherms and the pore size distribution
254 (not displayed), the evolution of specific surface area and pore volume followed
255 different trends on the examined samples. Thus, the reduction step provoked an increase

256 in the total surface area of 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ to 100 m² g⁻¹ and 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ to
257 111 m² g⁻¹ whereas the specific surface area decreased for the 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃
258 (62 m² g⁻¹) and NiAl₂O₄-D (48 m² g⁻¹) samples. The pore size distribution also indicated
259 that the pore volumes of the 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples were larger
260 after reduction, thereby suggesting that a considerable fraction of pores became
261 uncovered. By contrast, an inverse effect was observed in the case of the reduction of
262 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts [16].

263

264 3.2. Morphology

265 In order to visualise the textural aspects derived from the preparation method and Ni
266 loading the reduced samples were also investigated by scanning electron microscopy
267 (Figure S2). The micrograph of the reduced NiO sample was included for comparison.
268 Notable morphological differences were observed among the catalysts. Thus, the
269 micrograph of NiAl₂O₄-D revealed the presence of heterogeneous particles with rough
270 and irregular features. As for the 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ sample, small particles dispersed on
271 larger ordered ones with spherical shapes were observed. By contrast, well developed
272 and much larger particles were found on 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃
273 catalysts prepared by co-impregnation. It should be noted that the difference in aspect
274 between the reduced NiO bulk and the series of the reduced catalysts suggested that the
275 interaction of nickel with the support in all the analysed samples was relatively stronger.

276

277 3.3. Analysis of nickel phases

278 The four investigated samples, in oxidised and reduced states, were also characterised
279 by means of X-ray powder diffraction (XRD). The corresponding patterns are included
280 in Figure 1. The obtained crystalline phases were identified using the JCPDS files. The

281 profile of alumina sample calcined at 850 °C (JCPDS 79-1558) was included for
282 comparison. It should be noted that there were no changes in the transition alumina
283 structure after calcination in comparison with the as-received sample. The diagrams for
284 calcined NiAl₂O₄-D, 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃
285 catalysts showed remarkable differences with respect to pure alumina
286 (Figure 1 (a) samples). New diffraction peaks, assignable to a non-stoichiometric nickel
287 aluminate phase (NiAl₂O₄, JCPDS 78-1601), could be clearly observed with maxima at
288 $2\theta = 19.5^\circ, 31.7^\circ, 37.5^\circ, 45.3^\circ, 60.2^\circ$ and 65.8° [7,21]. Also the disappearance of the
289 signals related to the alumina structure was noted except for the 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃
290 catalyst. In addition, two typical peaks belonging to NiO (JCPDS 89-7131) appeared at
291 43.5° and 63.1° . However, the main peak of the aluminate phase coincided with the
292 second intense peak of NiO. Thus, the 37.5° peak may be the sum of the peaks of NiO
293 and aluminate. The pattern of 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ showed no lines of NiO, probably
294 because of the high dispersion of NiO and/or the fact that the crystallites were smaller
295 than their detection limit (about 2-5 nm) [7]. In addition to XRD the formation of nickel
296 aluminate could be also qualitatively assessed by the colour of the catalyst after
297 calcination. While bulk nickel oxide was green pure nickel aluminate phase was blue.
298 The 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples were blue, the 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃
299 catalyst was light blue and the NiAl₂O₄-D spinel became greenish-blue.

300 X-ray diffraction patterns of NiAl₂O₄-D, 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and
301 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ after reduction at 850 °C are also presented in Figure 1
302 ((b) samples). It was evidenced that Ni²⁺ (in NiAl₂O₄ and NiO) was completely reduced
303 into metallic Ni (JCPDS 89-7128, peaks at $44.6^\circ, 52^\circ$ and 76.5°) with the re-construction
304 of the alumina structure. As will be shown later, the presence of Ni²⁺ was considered to
305 be negligible in view of the UV-vis-DRS spectrum of NiAl₂O₄-D after reduction.

306

Figure 1

307 As a first approach Ni (111) ($2\theta = 44.6^\circ$) diffraction line broadening was used to
308 calculate the metallic Ni crystallite size by Scherrer equation. The FWHM was obtained
309 with WINPLOTR software. The results are given in Table 2. The estimation was not
310 possible for the reduced 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ sample due to the weak intensity of the
311 diffraction signal. Hence, the average size of Ni particles was found to be around 9.5 nm
312 on 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 11 nm on 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃. However, the reduction of the
313 NiAl₂O₄-D resulted in larger particles with an average size of about 22 nm. This result
314 could be probably explained by the reduction of large free NiO particles present in this
315 catalyst. This supposition was supported by the greenish-blue colour of the calcined
316 NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst as an indication of the presence of NiO free particles together with
317 the nickel aluminate phase. Note that these estimations for nickel crystallite size were in
318 good agreement with those obtained when using the peak at 52° (200) (Supporting
319 information, Table S1)

320

Table 2

321 Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was used to study the symmetry and the coordination
322 of nickel species dispersed on the catalysts. The Ni²⁺ (3d⁸) ions exhibited a simple
323 spectrum (³F fundamental term and ³P excited term) that involved three spin allowed d–
324 d transitions appearing in the near infrared (NIR) and in the visible domain. Moreover,
325 there was no Jahn Teller effect. These transitions are usually located around 930–
326 1660 nm for the ν_1 (³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}) transition, 570–1000 nm for ν_2 (³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g})
327 transition and 360–520 nm for ν_3 (³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P)) transition. The UV–visible-NIR
328 spectra of the calcined nickel catalysts are presented in Figure 2. The attribution of the
329 bands was carried out by comparison with bulk NiO used as reference. In the UV
330 region, the spectra of pure NiO and NiAl₂O₄-D exhibited a maximum around 267 nm

331 with a shoulder between 315-340 nm ascribed to $O^{2-} \rightarrow Ni^{2+}$ charge transfers. This band
332 was expectedly absent from the spectra of 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and
333 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples. In the visible domain, the bands located at 380 nm,
334 420 and 720 nm were assigned to the ν_3 and ν_2 transitions of Ni²⁺ ions of NiO in an
335 octahedral symmetry, while those at 550 nm and in the range of 600-645 nm were
336 related to the tetrahedrally coordinated Ni²⁺ species in the nickel aluminate lattice
337 [8,22,23]. These results were in agreement with the data of XRD analysis which showed
338 that the Ni phases of the calcined catalysts were composed of a mixture of NiO and non-
339 stoichiometric NiAl₂O₄ structure. Since the distribution of Ni²⁺ cations was between the
340 tetrahedral and octahedral sites of the spinel structure, the presence of defect/non-
341 stoichiometric spinel phase could be explained by the presence of NiAl₂O₄ structure in
342 the inverse coordination which may be formulated as Ni_{1-x}Al_x[Ni_xAl_{2-x}]O₄ (0<x<1)
343 [24,25].

344 In the NIR domain, the presence of Ni²⁺ in octahedral surrounding was confirmed. The
345 corresponding broad band located at 1135 nm, which tended to split in two bands
346 centred at 1100 and 1200 nm, could be attributed to the magnetic dipole
347 $3A_2g(F) \rightarrow 3T_2g(F)$ transition [26]. In 1350-1425 nm region, the spectra of
348 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ and 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalysts displayed several
349 bands due to ν_{OH} overtones of surface hydroxyl groups of the alumina support.
350 Correspondingly, the bands located at 1930 and 2220 nm were related to the vibration
351 modes of OH groups [27,28]. These bands were, as expected, absent in the spectrum of
352 NiAl₂O₄-D. On the other hand, according to the spectra of the catalysts recorded after
353 reduction, Ni²⁺ was reduced to Ni⁰. As a result, the bands attributed to Ni²⁺ in octahedral
354 and tetrahedral coordination disappeared.

355

Figure 2

356

357 3.4. Nickel surface characterisation

358 The different interactions of nickel species with alumina and spinel after calcination
359 were analysed by XPS measurements. In addition to the nature and oxidation state of
360 nickel species laying on the surface, XPS also offers valuable information regarding the
361 surface composition of the catalysts. For peak identification, the spectra were
362 deconvoluted on the basis of the constraints of equal spin-orbit splitting for Ni 2p peaks
363 and the area ratio of Ni 2p_{3/2} and Ni 2p_{1/2} being constant at approximately 2 (theoretical
364 value) [29]. For each sample, two photoemission peaks were shown: Ni 2p and O 1s
365 (Figure 3 A and B, respectively). The deconvolution of the main XPS peak in the
366 Ni 2p_{3/2} region displayed two peaks suggesting that Ni was at least distributed between
367 two sites (Figure 3A). Hence, the samples exhibited a typical band close to
368 854.4 ± 0.3 eV associated with NiO [9,30,31]. The position of this feature seemed to
369 depend on Ni content. The sample with the highest Ni loading (NiAl₂O₄-D) shifted the
370 peak attributed to NiO toward lower binding energies, probably because of the weak
371 interaction NiO/NiAl₂O₄. The second peak, present in all the Ni 2p spectra and located
372 between 856 and 857 eV, was assigned to Ni²⁺ ions in the network of NiAl₂O₄ phase
373 [9,30]. As aforementioned, the occurrence of NiAl₂O₄ spinel phase was in good
374 agreement with a number of earlier studies, which emphasised that the calcination of
375 Ni/Al₂O₃ samples at 825 °C or above may lead to the formation of the nickel aluminate
376 [32,33]. The spectra of all the analysed samples exhibited a typical shake-up satellite
377 peak close to 861.8 ± 0.5 eV.

378

Figure 3

379 The relative contribution of the deconvoluted peaks corresponding to NiAl₂O₄ and NiO
380 phases are summarised in Table 2. As for NiAl₂O₄-D sample its bulk heterogeneity

381 revealed by XRD was also confirmed at the surface level. When comparing the spectra
382 of 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, prepared by the same method but with a
383 different Ni content (5 and 24%, respectively), it was observed that the relative presence
384 of NiO increased with the metal loading. Regarding 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ and
385 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples, prepared by different routes but with the same Ni content
386 (24%Ni), it was found that on the 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ sample, 93.1% of nickel formed a
387 nickel aluminate phase, suggesting that the surface nickel was strongly bound to the
388 alumina support until completion of the monolayer and the excess nickel (6.9%) formed
389 NiO particles atop the nickel-alumina interface. However, in the case of
390 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst, the surface nickel distribution between the two sites
391 presented a roughly identical abundance (45.5% as NiO and 54.5% as NiAl₂O₄). On the
392 other hand, it could be noted that Ni/Al ratios appeared to have a similar trend on the
393 series of the catalysts in comparison with the data included in Table 1 determined by
394 WDXRF, despite the limitation of XPS to analyse only the elements laying on the
395 surface. Moreover, a significant enrichment of surface nickel was observed with
396 increasing Ni loading in the sample with the following trend:
397 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ (0.2) < 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ (0.7) ~ 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ (0.8) < NiAl₂O₄-D
398 (1).

399 The corresponding O 1s spectra of the catalysts are shown in Figure 3B. The spectra of
400 NiAl₂O₄-D, 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ indicated the presence of
401 multiple chemical environments. The O 1s signal could be decomposed into three
402 components: the first one at 528.6 ± 0.3 eV assigned to O²⁻ in NiO, the second situated
403 at 531 ± 0.3 eV and the third one located at high binding energies > 532 eV
404 characteristic of pure Al₂O₃ [32]. On the other hand, multiple assignments have been
405 given to the peak centred at 531 ± 0.3 eV [9,30,31,34]. Concerning our samples, the

406 correlation between the areas of Ni 2p (in NiAl₂O₄ phase) and O 1s at 531 ± 0.3 eV
407 clearly indicated that the assignment of this feature to NiAl₂O₄ phase was highly
408 possible. The O 1s peak of 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst could be decomposed with some
409 difficulty because of its apparent symmetry. The absence of the band attributed to
410 alumina pointed out that the near-surface region of this sample was composed mainly of
411 nickel aluminate together with small amounts of NiO. In view of the absence of pure
412 alumina phase and the stoichiometry, it could be concluded that a defect/non-
413 stoichiometric nickel aluminate phase was formed on 24%Ni/Al₂O₃.

414

415 3.5. Reducibility

416 H₂-TPR experiments were carried out in order to investigate the reducibility of the
417 nickel species and the metal-support interactions. In addition, this technique could help
418 in identifying the nickel phases present in each catalyst. In principle, a higher reduction
419 temperature would be expected for highly stabilised nickel species. The reducible NiO
420 species are usually divided into three types: α , β and γ [35-37]. The peak located in the
421 low temperature region (300 – 550 °C) was assigned to α -type NiO species, which were
422 free nickel oxides species having a weak interaction with the support (not shown). The
423 mild-temperature peak (550 – 700 °C) represented β -type NiO species with a stronger
424 interaction with alumina than α -type NiO. Finally, the high-temperature peak
425 (> 700 °C) was related to γ -type NiO species which were ascribed to the stable nickel
426 aluminate phase with a spinel structure.

427 Figure 4 shows the reduction profiles of supported and bulk nickel catalysts calcined at
428 850 °C. No reduction peaks were observed on the bare alumina support. Except for bulk
429 NiO, which was completely reduced about 600 °C, clearly two distinct reduction bands
430 were noted between 200 – 600 °C and between 600 – 950 °C. In order to characterise

431 the type of reducible nickel species present on the various catalysts, a Gaussian-type
432 deconvolution was applied. From this fitting procedure several reduction peaks could be
433 noticed. In the low temperature range the reduction of non stoichiometric NiO which
434 contains some Ni³⁺ (250 °C), and α-type NiO species (400 – 600 °C) occurred on the
435 supported catalysts [35,38]. It should be noted that the presence of reduction peaks
436 attributed to NiO on 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst confirmed that the NiO species, which
437 did not respond to X-ray diffraction due to their dispersion or small size, could be
438 characterised and quantified by H₂-TPR. However, the contribution of Ni₂O₃ could be
439 considered negligible in agreement with XRD patterns, which did not reveal a
440 measurable presence of this oxide. In view of the considerable H₂ uptake at very high
441 temperature (700 – 950 °C) the formation of nickel aluminate (γ-type NiO species) on
442 all the nickel/alumina catalysts was evidenced. As for the NiAl₂O₄-D sample it was
443 again confirmed that the spinel phase was non-stoichiometric with substantial amounts
444 of α and β species of NiO. The presence of an additional peak associated with β-type
445 NiO species was not clearly observed on the supported catalysts, although its presence
446 could not be ruled out. In sum, a more heterogeneous distribution of NiO phases was
447 found for NiAl₂O₄-D sample with respect to the alumina-supported catalysts, which
448 mostly contained just α- and γ-type species. Another two remarkable observations were
449 the following. On one hand, the reduction process of NiO species present on the
450 supported 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples was notably accelerated
451 with respect to the unsupported aluminate [39]. On the other hand, the NiAl₂O₄ phase
452 formed on 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ sample was more stable [16] and in turn required higher
453 reduction temperature in comparison with the 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst having the
454 same nickel content.

455 Figure 4

456 Table 2 shows the relative abundance of NiO and NiAl₂O₄ phases in each catalyst,
457 calculated on the basis of the H₂ consumed in each reduction band. Several conclusions
458 could be drawn from these results. Firstly, irrespectively of the Ni catalyst examined,
459 the most abundant nickel phase was nickel aluminate in line with the previous bulk
460 characterisation. For NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples the NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio inversely increased
461 with Ni content. Furthermore, a slightly larger presence of NiO was noted for
462 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ in comparison with 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ sample (both having the same
463 metallic content). Finally, when contrasting the NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio determined by both
464 bulk (H₂-TPR) and surface (XPS) techniques notable differences were evident for all the
465 samples, thereby revealing a marked heterogeneity in all of them. In other words, bulk
466 phase distribution could not be extrapolated towards the surface or vice versa.

467

468 3.6. Ni crystallite size

469 Alumina-supported nickel and NiAl₂O₄-D samples, reduced at 850 °C, were
470 investigated by high-angle annular dark-field scanning–transmission as well [40].
471 Figure 5 showed the corresponding HAADF-STEM micrographs and size distribution
472 diagrams. In all cases the particles displayed a quasi-spherical shape. The diagrams are
473 expressed in terms of frequency (%) as a function of particle size. The distribution of
474 the 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ samples presented an unimodal shape with an
475 average size of 6 and 11 nm, respectively. This corresponded to dispersion values of 21
476 and 12%, respectively. By contrast, a bimodal profile was obtained for the
477 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst with two peaks at 6 and 23 nm (with a corresponding
478 average particle size and dispersion of 19 nm and 12%, respectively). It is thought that
479 for this sample, with a low Ni content (below monolayer saturation), NiO (α -type
480 species) and NiAl₂O₄ (γ -type NiO species) crystallites were considerably separated on

481 the alumina surface. After reduction, the NiAl_2O_4 phase led to small nickel crystallites
482 (6 nm) while free NiO species resulted in notably larger crystallites (23 nm) (Figure 6)
483 [41]. However, in the case of the 70% $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and 24% $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ samples, the
484 surface of alumina support was considered to be fully covered by nickel phases (NiO
485 and NiAl_2O_4). The simultaneous reduction of both phases was then mutually restricted.
486 As a consequence, the resulting Ni particle size was comparatively smaller and
487 displayed a homogenous size distribution (Figure 6). Probably, the lower size obtained
488 for the 70% $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ sample was due to the less abundance of NiO (as determined
489 by H_2 -TPR) with respect to the 24% $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ sample. Therefore, it seems that reduction
490 of nickel atoms associated with aluminium atoms led to smaller nanocrystallites. As far
491 as bulk NiAl_2O_4 -D sample was concerned, its reduction led to crystallites with a broad
492 distribution size varying between 5 and 40 nm (with a corresponding average particle
493 size and dispersion of 19 nm and 4%, respectively). This was in line with the
494 simultaneous presence of either α -, β - and γ -type NiO species on this sample. Again the
495 lower size was attributed to the reduction of the aluminate phase whereas the larger size
496 was related to the reduction of NiO (α - and β -type species), as revealed by H_2 -TPR
497 analysis. The effect of the $\text{NiO}/\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4$ (as determined by H_2 -TPR) ratio on the
498 resulting Ni average crystallite size (as determined by HAADF-STEM) is depicted in
499 Figure 7. It was found that a lower size was favoured for low ratios.

500

Figure 5/Figure 6/Figure 7

501 The 70% $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ sample was additionally characterised by high-resolution
502 electron microscopy (HRTEM) (Supporting information, Figure S3). These images
503 evidenced the existence of small Ni nanoparticles that, according to the digital
504 diffraction pattern (DDP), could be indexed to the Ni FCC structure along the [011]
505 zone axis in good agreement with the XRD results. HRTEM images were also obtained

506 for the other catalysts but these were not included because there was little change in
507 comparison with the 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst.

508

509 *3.7. Acid properties*

510 Finally, the acid properties of the synthesised samples were characterised by means of
511 NH₃-TPD followed by dynamic thermogravimetry [42,43]. In addition to the thermal
512 stability study of pre-adsorbed NH₃, NH₃-TPD experiments also offered quantitative
513 information gained from the integration of TPD traces. Figure 8 and Table 1 summarise
514 the TPD-NH₃ results of the calcined and reduced samples. According to Table 1, the
515 amount of NH₃ desorbed from the support, γ -Al₂O₃, (630 $\mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ g}^{-1}$) was markedly
516 larger than that determined for the rest of the catalysts. The profile for the support
517 consisted of a first desorption peak, related to weak acid sites, at approximately 175 °C
518 accompanied by a second much more intense feature at 320 °C, the latter being probably
519 due to a large fraction of medium acid sites occurring at the alumina surface. The
520 dispersion of nickel onto the alumina surface along with the high-temperature (850 °C)
521 calcination dramatically decreased the amount of the adsorbed ammonia and slightly
522 shifted the main peak position from 320 °C to lower temperatures
523 (Figure 8, (a) samples). The TPD profiles for NiAl₂O₄-D, 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃,
524 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, appeared very similar, thus indicating that the
525 nature of the active sites involved in the adsorption of NH₃ was essentially the same on
526 all the samples. To facilitate the comparison in terms of surface acid density, the fourth
527 column in Table 1 included the quantitative data referred to 1 m² of surface area. It was
528 found that the influence of the preparation methods and the Ni content on acid density
529 was rather small. Thus, the surface density of the support, 4.7 $\mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$, was
530 comparable to that determined for 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ (4.5 $\mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$) and

531 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ (4.2 μmol NH₃ m⁻²). These results suggested that Ni was
532 incorporated into the Al₂O₃ network via diffusional substitution while the acid
533 properties of the surface remained unchanged [44].

534 Figure 8 also showed the TPD-NH₃ profiles of the reduced catalysts ((b) samples). In
535 comparison with the calcined samples, the second desorption peak shifted to high
536 temperatures. This shift was more noticeable for 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ (around 100 °C)
537 and implied that the reduction process led to the formation of stronger acid sites. The
538 data reported in Table 1 for reduced 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and
539 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples showed a remarkable loss of NH₃ adsorption sites around
540 60%, 29% and 19%, respectively. On NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst, as expected due to the
541 formation of Al₂O₃ after reduction, the surface acid density increased notably from
542 4.6 μmol NH₃ m⁻² (oxidised sample) to reach 5.7 μmol NH₃ m⁻² (reduced sample). In
543 the case of 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst the NH₃ adsorption density reached
544 3.3 μmol NH₃ m⁻² and the catalysts with the same Ni content, 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and
545 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, presented a lower acid surface density (3 μmol NH₃ m⁻² and
546 1.8 μmol NH₃ m⁻², respectively). This important decrease observed for these two
547 samples could be due to the high dispersion of metallic Ni obtained after reduction
548 process. It is believed that this metallic Ni covered the major part of the support surface
549 leaving the acid sites of the alumina practically unreachable. The homogeneity and high
550 dispersion of metallic nickel deduced from electron microscopy study are fully
551 consistent with the occurrence of a small fraction of surface acid sites in the
552 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ samples (Table 2).

553 Despite the significant loss of surface density of acid sites inherent to the dispersion and
554 reduction processes, the very much improved textural, structural, and chemical stability
555 of the resulting catalysts allows them to compete with bulk NiAl₂O₄-D sample

556 advantageously. Moreover, as shown in this work, the surface acidity of the supported
557 NiAl₂O₄ catalysts may be modulated by varying the Ni content in a wide range of
558 values, from 15 to 70%, with no dramatic loss of active sites.

559 Figure 8

560

561 *3.8. Catalytic behaviour of Ni-catalysts in steam reforming of methane*

562 Steam reforming of methane was chosen for a preliminary comparison of the reforming
563 efficiency of the investigated nickel catalysts. Catalytic performance was recorded
564 during 12.5 h at varying constant temperature (450 °C, 550 °C and 650 °C) with an
565 accumulated time on line of 63 h. The obtained results in terms of conversion (equation
566 1) and product distribution (equations 2-4) are summarised in Table 3. The evolution of
567 conversion with temperature is shown in Figure S4 (supplementary information). The
568 corresponding equilibrium data (white circles) and the conversion displayed by a
569 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ (Alfa Aesar, 132 m² g⁻¹) commercial catalyst are included as well. As a
570 general behaviour, the activity of the reduced catalysts (Figure S4) were characterised
571 by a low methane conversion at 450 °C followed by a sharp increase with reaction
572 temperature (550 °C and 650 °C). Furthermore, these nickel catalysts were stable and
573 exhibit a good catalytic performance irrespective of the reaction temperature.

574 Table 3

575 Among the examined nickel based catalysts, the best catalytic performance was
576 exhibited by 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and bulk NiAl₂O₄-D samples. Moreover, these
577 catalysts were markedly more active than 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ (61% and 53% vs. 46% at
578 650 °C, respectively) [14]. In view of the same metal loading of the supported catalysts
579 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, another remarkable observation was that a
580 significant difference in conversion was evident (61% vs. 42% at 650 °C) probably due

581 to the differences between each nickel metal particle size (6 nm vs. 11.2 nm,
582 respectively). Despite its larger crystallite size the high activity shown by the bulk
583 NiAl₂O₄-D sample was ascribed to the high nickel content (31wt.%).

584 As for the product distribution the reforming products were H₂, CO and CO₂. The
585 corresponding yield values at 450, 550 and 650 °C are included in Table 3. At low
586 temperature methane conversion was accompanied by the formation of hydrogen and
587 carbon dioxide with low amounts of carbon monoxide due to notable contribution of the
588 water gas shift reaction (CO+H₂O \leftrightarrow CO₂+H₂). On increasing temperature both H₂ and
589 CO yields, which were fairly stable with time, increased irrespective of the used
590 catalyst. Simultaneously, the Y(CO)/Y(CO₂) ratio was found to be higher. The
591 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst gave the highest yields at 650 °C, namely 1.32 for H₂ and
592 0.30 for CO. The corresponding H₂/CO ratio was 8.7.

593

594 **CONCLUSIONS**

595 Two series of nickel aluminates, unsupported and supported on alumina, catalysts were
596 synthesised and characterised by a wide number of analytical techniques including N₂-
597 physisorption, XRD, UV-visible-NIR, XPS, H₂-TPR, HAADF-STEM, HRTEM and
598 NH₃-TPD. The characterisation results of NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ samples, calcined at 850 °C,
599 indicated that the predominant surface nickel was in Ni²⁺ state and that the Ni surface
600 composition of all the catalysts was a mixture of NiO and NiAl₂O₄ structures. The
601 distribution of nickel between these two hosting sites depended on Ni loading and the
602 preparation method. The heterogeneous Ni composition was also evidenced for the bulk
603 nickel aluminate sample.

604 After reduction at high temperatures the nano-structural and chemical properties of the
605 supported catalysts were significantly modified by the interaction among the phases

606 lying on the carrier. A relationship between the Ni particle size and NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratios
607 was extracted in the examined samples. The smallest Ni particle size (6 nm), leading to
608 the highest dispersion, was obtained at low NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio corresponding to
609 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ catalyst prepared by co-impregnation method. These interesting
610 results allowed us to conclude that, in contrast to previous literature data, obtaining the
611 small metallic Ni particle size was not only a question of the abundance of nickel
612 aluminate phase, but it was controlled by the NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio initially present in the
613 calcined samples. Moreover, as shown in this work, the surface acidity of the supported
614 NiAl₂O₄ catalysts may be modulated by varying the Ni content in a wide range of
615 values, from 15 to 70%, with no dramatic loss of active sites.

616 Preliminary catalytic results on steam reforming of methane revealed that the
617 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ sample exhibited a higher activity and hydrogen yield than the other
618 investigated nickel based catalysts. This active behaviour was closely related to the
619 higher dispersion and smaller nickel crystallite size, which could eventually improved
620 the stability and the resistance toward sintering and carbon formation. Thus, the
621 advantages of dispersing nickel aluminate phase on a high surface area transition
622 alumina were fully confirmed. This provided a much better textural and nano-structural
623 stability than pure NiAl₂O₄ and allows the design of catalytic materials with the
624 possibility of tuning the chemical properties in accordance with the specific
625 requirements of the investigated reforming reactions.

626

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634

635 **SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION**

636 Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in online version.

637

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714 **CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES**

715 Table 1 Textural and acid properties of the synthesised nickel catalysts (calcined
716 and reduced samples).

717 Table 2 Relative abundance of NiO and NiAl₂O₄ phases on examined nickel
718 catalysts and NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio (as estimated by H₂-TPR), Ni⁰ crystallite
719 size for the reduced samples (as estimated by XRD and HAADF-STEM),
720 Ni dispersion (as estimated by HAADF-STEM) and results of XPS
721 analysis in the energy range of Ni 2p and O 1s of the calcined samples.

722 Table 3 Catalytic performance in terms of CH₄ conversion and yields of H₂, CO
723 and CO₂ of the catalysts for steam reforming of methane at different
724 temperatures. (reaction conditions: 38400 ml CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹;
725 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂; W=0.125 g).

726

727 Figure 1 XRD patterns of γ -Al₂O₃, (a) calcined samples and (b) reduced samples.

728 Figure 2 UV-vis-NIR spectra of the nickel catalysts: (a) 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, (b)
729 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, (c) 24%Ni/Al₂O₃, (d) NiAl₂O₄-D, (e) NiO and (f) Ni⁰
730 of reduced NiAl₂O₄-D.

731 Figure 3 XPS spectra of Ni 2p_{3/2} region (A) and O 1s region (B) of calcined (a)
732 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, (b) 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, (c) 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ and (d)
733 NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts.

734 Figure 4 H₂-TPR profiles of synthesised nickel catalysts.

735 Figure 5 HAADF-STEM images and metal particle size distribution of reduced (a)
736 15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, (b) 70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃, (c) 24%Ni/Al₂O₃ and (d)
737 NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts.

738 Figure 6 Reduction mechanism of NiO/NiAl₂O₄ based catalysts: (a) low Ni content,
739 (b) high Ni content.

740 Figure 7 Influence of the NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio (determined by H₂-TPR) on the Ni
741 particle size (determined by HAADF-STEM).

742 Figure 8 NH₃-TPD patterns of the synthesised calcined ((a) samples) and reduced
743 ((b) samples) nickel catalysts.

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Catalyst	Ni, wt.% ^a	Ni/Al atomic ratio ^a	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	d _p , Å	Total acidity, μmol NH ₃ g ⁻¹	Total acidity, μmol NH ₃ m ⁻²	Relative amount of strong sites, %
γ-Al ₂ O ₃	---	---	133	0.551	124	630	4.7	84.5
NiO Calcined	78	---	<1	0.001	132	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D Calcined	31	0.5	55	0.142	75	253	4.6	78.7
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D Reduced			48	0.124	81	274	5.7	89.6
24%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ Calcined	24	0.3	91	0.399	139	410	4.5	84.2
24%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ Reduced			100	0.434	138	179	1.8	60.5
70%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃ Calcined	24	0.3	75	0.272	113	318	4.2	86.5
70%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃ Reduced			62	0.244	122	188	3.0	86.9
15%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃ Calcined	5	0.05	111	0.492	140	440	4.0	77.3
15%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃ Reduced			121	0.506	132	394	3.3	76.9

^aDetermined by WDXRF

n.d. not determined

Table 1

Catalyst	%Ni as NiO*	%Ni as NiAl ₂ O ₄ *	NiO/NiAl ₂ O ₄ ratio*	Ni ⁰ crystallite size, nm		Dispersion, %	Ni, at. %	Ni/Al	Ni 2p _{3/2}			O 1s
				XRD	HAADF-STEM				Peak position, eV	Ni, % in the sites	Satellite, eV	Peak position, eV
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	40	60	0.66	22	18.5	4	18.3	1	854.1 (1)	61.7	861.3	528.5 (a)
									856.8 (2)	38.3		531.1 (b)
												532.6 (c)
24%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	34	64	0.53	9.5	11.2	12	14.9	0.7	854.4 (1)	6.9	862	528.3 (a)
									856.1 (2)	93.1		531.2 (b)
70%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃	25	73	0.34	11	6	21	15.3	0.8	854.2 (1)	45.5	861.6	528.7 (a)
									856.9 (2)	54.5		531.3 (b)
												533.2 (c)
15%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃	35	62	0.57	n.d.	19.1	4.5	6.7	0.2	854.6 (1)	3.7	862.2	528.8 (a)
									856.3 (2)	96.3		530.8 (b)
												531.9 (c)

*Determined by H₂-TPR analysis

n.d. not determined

(1) Ni²⁺ as NiO and (2) Ni²⁺ as NiAl₂O₄.

(a) O²⁻ as NiO, (b) O²⁻ as NiAl₂O₄ and (c) O²⁻ as Al₂O₃.

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Table 2

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Catalyst	X(CH ₄), %			Y(H ₂), %			Y(CO), %			Y(CO ₂), %		
	450 °C	550 °C	650 °C	450 °C	550 °C	650 °C	450 °C	550 °C	650 °C	450 °C	550 °C	650 °C
Equilibrium	40	74	97	0.79	1.37	1.68	0.04	0.23	0.51	0.37	0.51	0.46
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	9	29	53	0.23	0.71	1.14	0	0.07	0.27	0.08	0.22	0.26
24%Ni/Al ₂ O ₃	6	23	42	0.17	0.57	0.92	0	0.05	0.21	0.06	0.18	0.21
70%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃	4	26	61	0.11	0.65	1.32	0	0.05	0.3	0.04	0.21	0.31
15%NiAl ₂ O ₄ /Al ₂ O ₃	2	10	27	0.04	0.25	0.61	0	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.08	0.15
1%Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	5	21	46	0.12	0.47	0.97	0.01	0.07	0.24	0.04	0.13	0.22

Reaction conditions: 38400 ml CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂; W=0.125 g.

753

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Table 3

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 5

Low Ni Content
(15%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃)

769
770
771
772

(a)

High Ni Content
(70%NiAl₂O₄/Al₂O₃ and 24%Ni/Al₂O₃)

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776

(b)

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Figure 6

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Figure 7

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Figure 8